

ACETYLATION OF CELLULOSE AND LIGNIN IN JUTE FIBRE

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Jute fibre has been acetylated with acetic anhydride in the presence of acetic acid and potassium acetate, and acetylated cellulose as well as acetylated lignin isolated from the treated fibre. The degrees of acetylation of these components indicate that whereas the lignin became fully acetylated in a relatively short time, e.g. after boiling for 2 hours, the rate of acetylation of the cellulose was very much slower and was not complete after 48 hours under the conditions used. After a treatment lasting for 48 hours, the isolated lignin has a higher acetic acid content and a lower methoxyl content than that normally associated with lignin, and it is suggested that this increase in acetic acid content takes place at the expense of methoxyl groups. There are indications that polyuronide hemicelluloses are removed from the fibre during acetylation.

The treatment of jute with certain alkylating and acylating agents has been shown by Callow and Speakman (*J. Soc. Dyers & Col.*, 1949, 65, 758) to retard, or even inhibit, the discoloration which that fibre, like most lignocelluloses, undergoes on exposure to light. Partial acetylation seems to be particularly effective in this respect for, when the acetyl content of the fibre is raised sufficiently, it will undergo photochemical bleaching instead of discoloration as is the case with non-acetylated fibre. The suggestion has been made by Callow (*Nature*, 1947, 159, 309) that this bleaching is due to a bleaching agent, possibly acetyl peroxide, formed from the acetylated jute by the action of light. If this view is correct then the question arises as to which component of acetylated jute carries the labile acetyl groups from which a peroxide of this type is formed on exposure to light. Formation of such an agent might be expected to arise from degradation of either the acetylated cellulose or the acetylated lignin. Both are capable, in the isolated states, of forming acetyl derivatives and some evidence is available that, when a lignocellulose is treated with an acetylating mixture, both the cellulose and the lignin form acetyl derivatives. Fuchs (*Ber.*, 1928, 61B, 948), for example, was able to demonstrate the presence of acetylated cellulose and acetylated lignin in pine wood which had been treated with acetic anhydride in the presence of sulphuric acid. There are indications that these acetylated components exist in jute which has been treated with an acetylating agent. In this connection, Saha (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1947, 13, 339) has pointed out that the difference in the nature of X-ray diffraction patterns of acetylated ramie and jute fibres is due to the high percentage of lignin in raw jute and because of the co-existence of lignin acetate and cellulose acetate in acetylated jute, the crystal structure is different from that of pure cellulose acetate.

Apart, however, from establishing that both cellulose and lignin can be acetylated *in situ*, little or no information appears to be available as to the extent of acetylation of either components, especially during acetylation of raw jute. Saha (*loc. cit.*), for example, records the acetic acid content of the fibre

itself after acetylation and assumes, in later calculations, that this, or at least the greater part of it, is attached to cellulose.

In view of this paucity of information, the present work was carried out in an attempt to assess the extent to which cellulose and lignin became acetylated during treatment of raw jute fibre.

After acetylation, the fibre was fractionated into acetylated cellulose, prepared by the Cross and Bevan technique and acetylated lignin, isolated by means of acetic acid. Acetic acid contents of the acetylated fibre as well as those of the isolated fractions have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Raw jute fibre, of commercial grade, was used in these experiments and was freed from oils and waxes by extracting it with an alcohol-benzene mixture (1:2 v/v), washing in alcohol to remove the benzene, then in water and finally drying in air.

Acetylation.—As it was intended that the fibres, even after acetylation, should retain their fibrous form and yet attain a fairly high acetyl content, the method of fibrous acetylation described by Hess and Trogus (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, 15B, 157) was employed. Separate samples of air-dry fibre, each of 5 g., (moisture determined separately) were introduced into a flask containing 50 g. of glacial acetic acid, 200 g. of acetic anhydride and 60 g. of potassium acetate and refluxed for the required times. From the data provided by Saha (*loc. cit.*) it appeared that times of reflux of 2, 17 and 48 hours would be sufficient to give three stages of acetylation, and these times were therefore used. After treatment, the fibre was washed thoroughly in water and again dried in air.

Analysis of the Treated Samples.—After weighing and removing samples for determining moisture contents, changes in weight and acetic acid contents, the remainder was divided into two portions to be used for isolating a cellulose fraction and for isolation of lignin.

Determination of Acetic Acid Content.—This was carried out by adding 1.0*N* caustic soda solution (25 ml.) to about 0.4 g. of fibre which had been cut into short lengths, allowing to stand for 18 hours at room temperature, acidifying with 2.0*N* sulphuric acid (25 ml.) and steam distilling. Approximately 400 ml. of the distillate was collected and titrated against 0.1*N* caustic soda solution.

Isolation of Cellulose.—There are a number of references in the literature to the means of isolating acetylated cellulose from a lignocellulosic material which has first been acetylated. Fuchs (*loc. cit.*), for example, points out that when fully acetylated pine wood is extracted alternatively with chlorine and sodium bisulphite, as in the Cross and Bevan procedure, a residue of acetylated cellulose is obtained, and although the acetyl content may vary slightly in

different experiments, it is always very close to that of a cellulose triacetate. Suida and Titsch (*Ber.*, 1928, 61B, 1599) carried out a similar extraction on acetylated birch wood. Their results agree with those of Fuchs (*loc. cit.*) in that there is little loss of acetyl groups, providing that the solutions are non-alkaline. Because of these observations, it was proposed to isolate a cellulose fraction from acetylated jute by the Cross and Bevan method, making sure that the reagents were as neutral as possible, as for example, by extracting the chlorinated jute with a neutralised solution of sodium sulphite. The fibre (1.5 to 2 g.) was cut into small pieces, wetted-out with water and exposed alternately to chlorine gas (200 bubbles per min. for 15 mins.) and extracted with neutralised sodium sulphite solution (100 ml., 1%) on a boiling water-bath for 10 minutes. Treatment with chlorine and sodium sulphite was continued until no colour developed on adding the sulphite to the chlorinated sample. The product was finally filtered through a sintered glass crucible (porosity 1), washed with water and dried over phosphorus pentoxide *in vacuo*.

Extraction of Lignin.—In order to retain the acetyl groups attached to lignin, extraction was carried out along the lines recommended by Suida and Titsch (*loc. cit.*). In this, about 3 g. of the air-dry fibre was refluxed for 2 hours with glacial acetic acid (75 ml.) containing 0.25% (v/v) of concentrated hydrochloric acid, filtered through a crucible of porosity 1 and the fibre washed twice with glacial acetic acid using 25 ml. for each washing. The filtrate and the washings were concentrated under reduced pressure to about 25 ml. and the concentrate poured into 300 ml. of water with mechanical stirring. The mixture was boiled for 5 minutes to coagulate the precipitate which was filtered on a sintered crucible of porosity 4, washed with water and dried over phosphorus pentoxide *in vacuo*.

Acetic acid contents of the isolated cellulose and isolated lignin were determined as, for the fibre using about 0.3 g. of isolated cellulose and about 0.1 g. of isolated lignin in each case.

Methoxyl Content of Isolated Lignin.—Methoxyl values of the isolated lignins were estimated after saponifying them with 1.0*N* caustic soda solution and reprecipitating with an excess of 1.0*N* hydrochloric acid. The methoxyl contents were determined by a modification of the Ziesel method, described by Vieböck and Brecher (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 3207) and which consisted of oxidising the methyl iodide, evolved on distillation with hydriodic acid in the presence of phenol, with bromine and determining the amount of iodic acid so formed.

DISCUSSION

Acetylation of Jute.—Data relating to increases in weight and acetic acid contents of the treated fibre are shown in Table I.

Though the method of acetylation is similar, though not identical, to that used by Saha (*loc. cit.*), it is noted that the degrees of acetylation differ

considerably in the two cases. The acetic acid content of these samples, for example, is considerably higher after 2 hours' treatment and appreciably lower

TABLE I

Acetylation of jute fibre.

Time.	Weight of sample used.	% Gain in weight.	% Acetic acid.
0	4.592 g.	...	3.83
2 hrs.	4.601	20.3	28.9
17	4.571	24.5	32.3
48	4.612	31.5	38.3

at treatments of 17 and 48 hours. While the difference in techniques employed, in that in Saha's experiment there was a progressive increase in liquid to fibre ratio, would probably account for a higher degree of acetylation in the later stages, no explanation can be offered for the greater acetylation in 2 hours during the present work.

Isolation of Cellulose.—Delignification of jute and isolation of the Cross and Bevan cellulose from it, have been shown by Callow (*Nature*, 1950, 166, 1040) to be more difficult from partly acetylated jute than from the raw fibre in that many more treatments are necessary. A similar difficulty was experienced during this work, for while cellulose could be isolated from raw jute after three chlorinations and extractions with neutralised sulphite, the acetylated samples required many more and even after ten successive treatments with chlorine and sulphite solution, an absolutely pure-white pulp could not be obtained from the most highly acetylated sample. The colour reactions associated with lignin after chlorination and addition of sulphite are also less characteristic in the case of the acetylated material. Unlike the non-acetylated sample, in which an intense red colour develops in the cold immediately on adding sulphite to the chlorinated lignin, the solution containing an acetylated sample must be warmed, or even boiled, before any colour develops. Because of this, it is more difficult to assess the point when delignification of acetylated jute is complete but, as far as can be ascertained, the isolated celluloses are free from lignin. The yields and acetic acid contents are shown in Table II.

There are two points of interest in these results. In the first place, it is seen that the isolated cellulose fractions have acetic acid contents of 27.5%, 31.9% and 37.0% after treatments with the acetylating mixture lasting for 2, 17 and 48 hours respectively. Since the acetic acid saturation value of cellulose is 62.5%, these represent 44.0%, 51.0% and 59.2% of this saturation value respectively. In the second place, the percent yields of acetyl-free cellulose have been

TABLE II

Isolated cellulose from acetylated jute.

Time of acetylation.	Yield of acetylated cellulose.	Acetic acid in cellulose.	Yield of cellulose (calc.)	
			(a)	(b)
0	68.8%	...	68.8%	68.8%
2 hrs.	82.7	27.5%	66.4	79.9
17	82.9	31.9	62.9	78.3
48	84.9	37.0	62.4	82.1

(a) As percent of acetylated product.

(b) As percent of original jute:

calculated on an original jute basis and show that, after acetylation, higher values are obtained in each case.

Though the chlorinating method of isolating cellulose, as in the Cross and Bevan technique, is known to give a non-homogeneous product consisting of true cellulose with associated pentosans, the method is more or less specific in that it removes lignin and polyuronide hemicelluloses. Assuming that these chlorinating reagents also remove lignin and polyuronides specifically from acetylated jute, it seems likely that because acetylated jute contains a higher percentage of structural celluloses, it probably contains a lower percentage of hemicelluloses of the polyuronide type. If this view is correct then it seems likely that removal of the latter from the fibre takes place during the process of acetylation.

Isolation of Lignin.—As in the case of cellulose, noticeable differences occur when lignin is isolated from raw or from acetylated jute. Raw fibre, for example, on refluxing with a mixture of acetic and hydrochloric acids, as indeed with all mineral acids, rapidly assumes a pink colour. Acetylated jute does not do this, but remains light in colour and the extracted material, after washing with acetic acid, is lighter in colour than the original.

TABLE III

Isolation of lignin from acetylated jute.

Time of acetylation.	Yield of acetylated lignin.	Acetic acid in lignin.	Yield of lignin (calc.)		Methoxyl content of saponified lignin.
			(a)	(b)	
0	9.00%	12.4%	8.20%	8.20%	17.9
2 hrs.	7.49	33.7	5.68	6.83	17.9
17	7.85	33.7	5.95	7.41	15.3
48	8.45	38.5	6.12	8.05	9.77

(a) As percent of acetylated product.

(b) As percent of original jute.

In agreement with the work of Brauns and Buchanan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 645) on spruce wood, lignin isolated from raw fibre by acetic acid has an appreciably high acetic acid content. A similar observation with both spruce and birch lignin has led Bell and Wright (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1949, 27B, 572) to conclude that lignin in both gymnosperms and angiosperms contains, *in situ*, an α -hydroxy- β -methoxyisobutyl group which is acetylated when the lignin is extracted with acetic acid.

Lignin isolated from jute, which had been methylated for 2 and 17 hours, had the same acetic acid content of 33.7%. This figure is of the same order as that generally associated with lignin which has first been isolated and then acetylated. Acetic acid contents ranging from 31% to 32.5% have been recorded, for example, by Heuser and Ackerman (*Cellulose Chem.*, 1924, 5, 13) for Willstätter lignin isolated from spruce wood and then acetylated with acetic anhydride in the presence of nitric acid, or pyridine, or with acetyl chloride. Acetic acid and pyridine have also been used by Sarkar (*this Journal*, 1935, 12, 547) for acetylating lignin isolated from jute. The acetic acid content reported by this author appears to depend on the method used for isolating the lignin, for figures ranging between 28.9% and 33.5% are quoted.

Treatment of jute for 48 hours, before isolating the lignin, however, leads to a higher acetic acid content of the isolated lignin, the value being somewhat higher than that normally associated with lignin. A similar high value has previously been recorded by Heuser and Ackerman (*loc. cit.*) in the case of isolated lignin, for when this is acetylated for a prolonged time, the acetyl content increases and the methoxyl content diminishes. A similar reaction appears to take place in the case of acetylated jute for when the methoxyl contents of the isolated lignins were determined after saponification with dilute caustic soda, the methoxyl content was found to be lowest for that sample which had been treated with the acetylating mixture for the longest time.

It would appear from this that the lignin present in jute is completely acetylated after a short time of treatment. Prolonging the treatment leads to a higher acetyl content, but this takes place at the expense of the methoxyl groups which the lignin contains, probably by fission of these groups and acetylation of the hydroxyl groups so formed.

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